

Deliverable D4.4

Protocol for fish authenticity and origin
based on stable isotope approach

DATE: MAY 31, 2024

DELIVERABLE NUMBER: D4.4

Co-funded by the
European Union

General Information

Call identifier: HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-10
 GA Number: 101060712
 Start date of project: 01/06/2022
 Work Package: WP4
 Type: Deliverable
 Number: D4.4
 Version: 1
 Due Date: 31/05/2024
 Submission date: 31/05/2024

Responsible Organization: JSI

Prepared by: Nives Ogrinc, Marjeta Mencin, Brina Pavlovič, Lidija Strojnik, Doris Potočnik, Robert Modic, Matevž Ogrinc, Andraž Simčič, Barbara Koroušič Seljak

Dissemination Level: Public

Document Type		
PRO	Technical/economic progress report (internal work package reports indicating work status)	
DEL	Technical reports identified as deliverables in the Description of Work	X
MoM	Minutes of Meeting	
MAN	Procedures and user manuals	
WOR	Working document, issued as preparatory documents to a Technical report	
INF	Information and Notes	

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CON	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium	

Disclaimer: © 2024 by FishEUTrust

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them.

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

ABT	AquaBio Tech, Malta
AI	Artificial Intelligence
C	Carbon
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CETGA	Centro Tecnológico del Cluster de la Acuicultura, Spain
CLL	Co-creation Living Labs
DD-SIMCA	Data-Driven Soft Independent Modelling of Class Analogy
EU	European Union
FoM	Figure of Merit
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
H	Hydrogen
ICP-MS	Inductivity Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
IoT	Internet of Things
IPMA	Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera, Portugal
IRMS	Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometry
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry
LDA	Linear Discriminant Analysis
N	Nitrogen
O	Oxygen
OCC	One-Class Classifier
OPLS-DA	Orthogonal Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis
PLS-DA	Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis
S	Sulphur
SD	Score Distance
SOPs	Standard Operational Procedures
SRIA	Stable Isotope Ratio Analysis
USGS	United States Geological Survey
V-CDT	Vienna Cañon Diablo Troilite
V-PDB	Vienna-Pee Dee Belemnite
V-SMOW	Vienna-Standard Mean Ocean Water
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations.....	3
Table of Contents.....	4
Executive Summary.....	5
1 Introduction.....	6
1.1 Scope of the deliverable.....	6
1.2 Structure of the deliverable.....	6
2 Definitions.....	7
3 Background.....	8
4 Sampling strategy.....	11
4.1 Integrity of sampling.....	11
4.2 Sample traceability and associated metadata.....	12
4.3 Sampling fish and other seafood.....	14
4.4 Sample integrity during transport and storage.....	15
4.5 Handling of samples on arrival at the test laboratory.....	16
5 Analytical methods.....	16
5.1 Sampling.....	17
5.2 Sample preparation.....	18
5.3 Stable isotope analysis.....	18
5.3.1 Determination of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in fish sample water.....	19
5.3.2 Determination of the isotopic composition of bulk C, N and S in fish and mussel samples.....	19
5.4 Multi-elemental analysis using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry.....	20
6 IsoFoodTrack database.....	21
7 Real-life application performed in FishEUTrust.....	24
7.1 Data visualization.....	24
7.2 Statistical evaluation of the data and modelling.....	25
8 Conclusions.....	31
9 References.....	32

Table of Tables

Table 1. Summary of references on fish and seafood authenticity and origin based on stable isotope approach.....	9
Table 2. Advantages and disadvantages of chilling and freezing (Shawyer et al., 2003).....	15
Table 3. The list of samples analyzed by the developed FishEUTrust protocol.....	17

Table of Figures

Figure 1. Generic sea-to-fork chain map for fish and seafood (adopted by Kresna et al., 2017).....	13
Figure 2. Protocol for determination of stable isotope composition in fish fillets and gills.....	18
Figure 3. Protocol for determination of stable isotope composition in mussels.....	19
Figure 4. Protocol for determination of elemental composition in fish fillets, gills and mussels.....	20
Figure 5. Example of the structure of the database in Excel with selected categories.....	22
Figure 6. Interface of IsoFoodTrack database.....	22
Figure 7. The structure of the database.....	23
Figure 8. A schematic of the proposed database structure outlining how contributors and users would interface with samples, analyses, measurements, and datasets to describe stable isotope data.....	24
Figure 9. Graphical presentation (google map) of stable isotope data of light elements on fish and mussels from CLLs.....	24
Figure 10. Relationship between $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in farmed and wild fish fillets from different countries a) with Malta wild samples; b) without wild samples from Malta.....	26
Figure 11. OPLS-DA (SIMCA): differentiation of fish samples based on production type (farmed vs wild) including only stable isotope variables in all countries (Malta wild samples were excluded).....	27
Figure 12. Box plots of the most powerful parameters responsible for differentiation between farmed and wild mussels.....	27
Figure 13. OPLS-DA score plots in the pairwise comparisons between different types of mussel production farmed vs wild. The ellipse on the score plot represents the 95% confidence interval.....	28
Figure 14. Discriminant function score plot for fish a) gills and b) fillet discriminating country of origin based on stable isotope data.....	28
Figure 15. OPLS-DA score plots in comparisons between different countries of origin: a) the whole dataset with wild and farmed; b) only farmed samples. The ellipse on the score plot represents the 95% confidence interval.....	29
Figure 16. a) OPLS-DA score plots and b) VIP values in comparisons between different countries of origin for farmed and wild fish. The ellipse on the score plot represents the 95% confidence interval. The red dotted line indicates the criteria for identifying the variables, which is important for the developed model.....	30
Figure 17. DD-SIMCA classification model of a) authentic fish samples (green dots; n = 55) from Portugal (wild and farmed samples), b) fish samples (red dots; n = 98) from outside Portugal (wild and farmed samples from Spain, Malta, Slovenia, Croatia). The green line signifies the acceptance area at $\alpha = 0.05$	30

Executive Summary

Deliverable D4.4, linked to T4.2, focuses on developing a protocol to verify the type of production and country of origin (authenticity) of seafood using stable isotopes and elemental composition as part of the FishEUTrust. Such a protocol is needed because honest labelling and safeguarding the seafood chain from fraud is paramount for consumer confidence, industry fairness, and supply chain resilience. Mislabeling and fraud are significant issues in the fishery and aquaculture sectors, prompting the need for robust traceability systems.

The protocol covers all the essential steps, including a comprehensive sampling strategy, maintaining sample integrity throughout the supply chain, appropriate sample handling procedures in testing laboratories, analytical methods, database formation and statistical evaluation of results. These steps are essential to ensuring the reliability of a seafood authenticity database.

Fit for purpose analytical methods for the determination of stable isotope ratios of light elements, including $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$ determination (expressed as $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) in fish sample water and $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$, $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$, $^{34}\text{S}/^{32}\text{S}$ (expressed as $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$) in fillets and gills are described. Elemental analysis using ICP-MS further complemented the isotopic data, enhancing the discriminatory power of the analytical approach. Moreover, the strengths and limitations of these analytical techniques need to be well understood.

Also described is the implementation of the IsoFoodTrack database, a centralized repository for storing and analyzing the large amounts of project data generated. Such a database is essential because Stable Isotope Ratio Analysis (SIRA) is a comparative technique requiring authentic sample databases against which test sample results are compared and the data visualization tools used for interpreting trends and patterns within the dataset and statistical analyses (LDA, OPLS-DA, and DD-SIMCA) enabling the classification and discrimination of samples based on their production methods and geographical origin.

Key findings include the differentiation between wild and farmed fish based on stable isotopes, with higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values observed in wild specimens. Geographical discrimination was also achieved based on distinct isotopic signatures, where $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ was identified as a key differentiating parameter. The model's accuracy for verifying the country of origin was also improved by including elemental composition. The study also verified the origin of fish samples, specifically whether they come from Portugal, using DD-SIMCA. The classification model demonstrated good sensitivity (93%) and excellent specificity (98%), with an overall accuracy of 96%.

The study has shown that while SIRA has some limitations, it has real potential to verify country of origin labeling claims and support food law enforcement when used alongside traceability and other confirmatory evidence. Although the established traceability system was tested on economically important species like sea bream (*Sparus auratus* L.) and mussels, it is readily adaptable for other seafood and food sectors of plant and animal origin. This adaptability highlights the developed protocol's broad applicability and future potential in ensuring the integrity of various food supply chains.

1 Introduction

Currently, seafood represents a significant portion of global animal protein production, with aquaculture being a key source. Farmed fish is a sustainable alternative to fisheries since it allows the maintenance of the quality and nutritional values of fish from fisheries while maintaining the ecological equilibrium of the sea. Fish farming is widespread, and although the product quality is of the highest standard, traceability tools applied to fish farming require substantial improvement. FishEUTrust set out to bridge this gap by developing tools integrating metagenomic, genetic, chemical, and stable isotope approaches (WP4) in addition to digital solutions based on the Internet of Things (IoT) and blockchain/digital passports developed (WP7). The aim is to safeguard the quality, safety and traceability of seafood products within the European seafood supply chain, affording European consumers a higher level of trust in seafood products placed on the market. In the case of WP4, the work was divided into the following tasks:

1. Task 4.1 Develop a Metagenomics Sequencing Toolbox for determination the origin, of seafood products, and test protocols to determine freshness, pathogens, and antibiotic resistance
2. Task 4.2 Devise an alternative methodology to certify fish authenticity and origin using a stable isotope approach.
3. Task 4.3 Establishing protocols and standard operational procedures (SOPs) for determining freshness, pathogenicity, and antibiotic resistance.
4. Task 4.4 Creating a data platform to establish seafood origin, safety, quality, and sustainability to boost consumer uptake and trust.

This deliverable relates to T4.2 and describes the development of a protocol for seafood authenticity and origin based on a stable isotope approach.

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable *D4.4, Protocol for fish authenticity and origin based on a stable isotope approach*, aims to **develop and publish a robust protocol for determining fish and seafood authenticity and origin based on elemental composition and stable isotopes. The construction of an authenticity database based on authentic fish and seafood reference samples is also presented.**

The FishEUTrust traceability system based on using stable isotopes includes three steps: 1) the development of suitable analytical methods; 2) the establishment of a database of authentic samples; and 3) data processing using chemometric approaches. Further, the protocol defines a practical process for obtaining reference samples at different points in the fish and seafood supply chain. It specifies what associated recording, documentation and other considerations are necessary for a sample to be deemed acceptable for inclusion in the fish and seafood authenticity database. Moreover, as fish and seafood are globally traded commodities, it should be noted that this protocol does not consider any legal definitions of fish and seafood and thus does not include a specification for its compositional requirements.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The content of this deliverable is structured as follows:

- Sections 2 and 3 describe the definitions and background needed to establish an appropriate traceability system for seafood.
- Section 4 is related to the sampling strategy and includes sampling integrity, sample traceability and associated metadata, sampling fish and other seafood, sampling integrity during transport and storage and handling of samples in the test laboratory.

- Section 5 is related to analytical methods for stable isotope and elemental analysis and presents the analysis performed in FishEUTrust.
- Section 6 presents the IsoFoodTrack database.
- Section 7 shows the real-life application performed in FishEUTrust and the evaluation of results with relevant statistical models.

The final chapter is related to Conclusions.

2 Definitions

The following is a list of some relevant definitions:

Authenticity: Refers to its genuineness and intactness, implying that the food complies with its label description. It is a term that also encompasses features, such as the origin (specific, geographic or genetic), production management system (conventional, organic, traditional practices, free-range) and processing technology.

Food fraud: CEN Workshop Agreement 86 Food fraud: *intentionally causing a mismatch between food product claims and product characteristics.*

CX/FICS 18/24/7 Food fraud: *any deliberate action of businesses or individuals to deceive others regarding the integrity of food to gain undue advantage. Types of food fraud include but are not limited to adulteration, substitution, dilution, tampering, simulation, counterfeiting, and misrepresentation.*

Traceability: Traceability or product tracing is defined by the Codex Alimentarius Commission as “the ability to follow the movement of a food through specified stage(s) of production, processing and distribution”.

Stable isotopes: Isotopes are atoms of the same element with the same chemical properties but different masses because of the different numbers of neutrons in the nucleus. Stable isotopes are those isotopes that do not decay and thus emit no ionizing radiation into the environment.

Isotope composition: The isotopic composition is the different isotopes of which something is composed. The stable isotope ratio measurements were performed using Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometry (IRMS) and expressed in the δ – notation in ‰ according to:

$$\delta(^i/^j E) = \delta^{i/j} E = \frac{^{i/j} R_P - ^{i/j} R_{Ref}}{^{i/j} R_{Ref}}$$

Where superscripts i and j denote the higher and the lower atomic mass number of element E , R_P and R_{Ref} represent the ratios between the heavier and the lighter isotope ($^2\text{H}/^1\text{H}$, $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$, $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$, $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$, $^{34}\text{S}/^{32}\text{S}$) in the sample (P) and reference material (Ref), respectively. The $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ were reported relative to the V-SMOW (Vienna-Standard Mean Ocean Water) standard, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values were reported relative to the V-PDB (Vienna-Pee Dee Belemnite) standard, while $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ were reported relative to AIR and the V-CDT (for Vienna Cañon Diablo Troilite) standard, respectively.

Isotope fractionation: Isotope fractionation is the change in isotope ratios of reaction products compared to the reactants during a chemical reaction (e.g., oxidation and dissolution) or phase transition (e.g., melting and evaporation).

Fingerprint/signature: The fingerprint or signature combines δ -values of one or more elements, elemental ratios or other measured parameters that characterize the compound or produce.

3 Background

The link between food and territory has gradually been lost over time due to changing food production and transportation technologies, as well as consumer exposure to non-local culinary experiences through travel and the media (Luykx and van Ruth, 2008). In response, consumer demand for high-quality, culturally distinctive products is growing worldwide, along with concerns about food authenticity, geographic origin, health and nutrition, and sustainable production.

Among the exploitable techniques (Danezis et al., 2016), stable isotope and elemental fingerprinting are leading the way in establishing the authenticity and geographical origin of food products (Kelly et al., 2005; Drivelos & Georgiou, 2012; Danezis et al., 2016). The basis of stable isotope approach lies in the transfer of the isotopic signals (isotopic fingerprint) of bio-elements (H, C, N, O, S) present in local feed and water to animal and plant tissue, processes that are in the main well understood. Each of these elements has at least two stable isotopic forms, and the ratio of these forms can vary significantly in water and the environment at different locations. These measurements are performed using IRMS. In addition to isotopes, element concentrations in plants and animals (elemental fingerprints) are also used to check food authenticity and include not only macro-elements (e.g., sodium, calcium, potassium) and trace-elements (e.g., copper, zinc and selenium) but also rare earth elements (e.g., lanthanum, cerium, samarium) and others that occur in low abundance (iridium, gold).

Determining authenticity also requires a suitable reference dataset of analyzed authentic products, representing a significant drawback in time and cost since such a dataset must comprise sufficient samples of a product representative of a wide range of geographical, seasonal, dietary and production conditions (Kelly et al., 2005). Authenticity is evaluated by comparing values found in commercial samples with the limits estimated based on the dataset. These values are evaluated for best fit using a suitable statistical model. As this approach depends on comparing an unknown sample with a database of authentic samples of known origin, the quality of the database is central to the reliability of the method and, currently, only a few databases cover a wide regional distribution of isotopic signatures, among which the European wine database is currently the most developed (Camin et al., 2017).

Authentication of fishery and aquaculture products is of growing interest due to the expansion and globalization of the fish value chain. According to EU Legislation (Regulation (EU) No 1379/2013), label descriptions of fish must include commercial designation, scientific name of species, production method and fishing area of provenance. Frequently, this information is unreliable and requires proper validation to ensure compliance with food legislation and traceability requirements and protect consumers from commercial food fraud. Although there are regulations for correct labelling, fish and other seafood remain the most mislabelled foodstuffs globally (Reilly, 2018; Mazarakioti et al., 2022). There are also price differences between “farmed” and “wild” fish of various species, e.g., salmon, which makes mislabeling farmed fish as wild financially attractive. Fish and seafood fraud also includes falsified information about its geographical origin and production method, which has a negative economic and environmental impact. Notably, the mislabelling of products poses a risk to public health by the illegal commercialization of some poisonous and toxic species.

The ability to discriminate between fish and seafood derived from fisheries or aquaculture can be achieved by identifying specific tracers or markers, such as a stable isotope approach. Stable isotopes in aquaculture are still mainly related to carbon and nitrogen-stable isotopes commonly used as dietary source biomarkers (Takizawa et al., 2020; Twining et al., 2020). The foods they consume directly affect the stable isotope composition of aquatic animals, meaning that the formulated diets and the pond’s natural productivity of semi-intensively farmed fish will produce a significantly different isotopic signature compared with wild ones. Between carbon and nitrogen, the latter is greatly fractionated during dietary assimilation. Enrichment of a heavier isotope is increased by 2-4% with each trophic level, thus making it very useful when specifying

organisms' trophic levels. $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values vary among species and are influenced by different diets and stress (Zhang et al. 2019).

Also, the new science of food forensics involves developing isotopic techniques that can detect the adulteration and counterfeiting of fish. As stated previously, this approach's strength relies on having fit-for-purpose databases that contain data derived from 'authentic' reference fish and seafood samples that fully represent their defined scope. Therefore, the homogeneity, integrity, and provenance of fish and seafood reference samples used to compile such databases must be assured. To date, no documented protocol has been published containing recommendations and requirements for collecting fish and seafood reference samples for verification of authenticity. This work aims to address this critical deficiency.

Developing a suitable protocol meant the following:

- Conducting a literature review (academic and grey) of relevant published documents listed in Table 1 and section References.
- Given the complexities involved in such a task, adopt a pragmatic and realistic approach to sampling.

Table 1. Summary of references on fish and seafood authenticity and origin based on stable isotope approach

Species	Origins	Method/ isotopes	Reference
FISH			
FISH	Bahamas (Cape Eleuthera)	EA-IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Zhu et al., 2019
FISH (Atlantic cod (<i>Gadus morhua</i>) and saithe (<i>Pollachius virens</i>))	Norway	IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Oliveira et al., 2011
FISH (<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>)	ITALY (commercial farms)	CF-EA-IRMS/ $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$	Tulli et al., 2020
FISH (<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>)	FARMED (Machrihanish Marine Environmental Research Laboratory in Kintyre, Scotland and wholesaler (Glasgow) WILD (southern England)	EA-IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Bell et al., 2007
FISH (<i>Lates calcarifer</i>)	Australia, Malaysia	CF-EA-IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Gopi et al., 2019
FISH (<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>)	Farms located in different Italian areas	IRMS/ $\delta^2\text{H}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ "	Camin et al., 2018
FISH (<i>Pampus argenteus</i> , <i>Trachinotus ovatus</i>)	China (seven different representative locations)	IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Ni et al., 2022
FISH (<i>Salmo trutta</i> , <i>Salmo salar</i> , <i>Oncorhynchus nerka</i> , <i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>)	Bought in German market or at conventional and organic fish farms (aquacultured salmon originated from Ireland, Scotland and Norway; wild salmon originated from Alaska)	EA-IRMS/ $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Molkentin et al., 2015
FISH (salmonids: <i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i> , <i>Salmo salar</i>)	China and Chile cultured in freshwater and seawater	EA-IRMS/ $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$	Han et al., 2021

FISH (<i>Scomber japonicas</i> , <i>Larimichthys polyactis</i> , <i>Larimichthys crocea</i> and <i>Theragra chalcogramma</i>)	seafood market in Korea	EA-IRMS/ $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Kim et al., 2015
FISH ROE (<i>Avgotaracho Messolongiou</i>)	Four different regions: two from Greece, one from Australia and one from Mauritania	EA-IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$	Tsirogiannis et al., 2022
SEAFOOD			
CHINESE MITTEN CRAB (<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i>)	China (lower reaches of the Yangtze River)	IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Luo et al., 2019
CLAMS (<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>)	Three different lagoons along the Italian northern Adriatic coast within the delta of the Po river	EA-IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Bianchini et al., 2021
CRAYFISH (<i>Procambarus clarkii</i>)	CHINA (Guangdong Province, Hunan Province and Hubei Province)	EA-IRMS/ $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Xia et al., 2022
JELLYFISH (<i>Rhopilema esculentum</i> , <i>Nemopilema nomurai</i>)	China (farm in Haizhou Bay, Yangtze Estuary)	EA-IRMS/ $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Wang et al., 2021
MUSSELS (<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>)	Spain, Portugal, France, Italy, Tunisia, and Chile: located in the Mediterranean Sea, the European Atlantic coast and the Chilean Pacific coast	EA-IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	del Rio-Lavín et al., 2022
OCTOPUS (<i>Octopus berrima</i> , <i>Octopus pallidus</i> ; <i>Amphioctopus aegina</i>)	South-east Asia and southern Australia	IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ - in statoliths	Martino et al., 2022
PRAWN (<i>Penaeus monodon</i>)	Australia and four Asian countries: China, India, Indonesia and Malaysia	CF-EA-IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Gopi et al., 2019
SCALLOPS (<i>Patinopecten yessoensis</i> , <i>Chlamys farreri</i> , and <i>Argopecten irradians</i>)	China (two different sea areas: Bohai Sea and Yellow Sea)	IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Zhang et al., 2019
SEA CUCUMBER (<i>Apostichopus japonicus</i>)	North China Sea	IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Zhang et al., 2017
SEA URCHIN (<i>Mesocentrotus nudus</i>)	North Yellow Sea (Longwang tang, Penglai, Xiaoping dao, Lidao, and Dandong Bay)	EA-IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$	Dong et al., 2022
SQUID (<i>Dosidicus gigas</i>)	Eastern Pacific Ocean	IRMS/ bulk $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	Gong et al., 2018

4 Sampling strategy

Any adopted sampling strategy for obtaining fish and seafood reference samples to build an authenticity database must reflect its desired scope and objectives. Determining the geographical origin of fish and seafood is challenging and requires innovative, cost-effective approaches.

Consideration should be given to the practicality of obtaining relevant samples in statistically relevant numbers, defined by established and declared statistical best practices. The use of market import and sales data can assist in structuring such sampling strategies, i.e., identifying species of commercial importance in a particular country/region / or a company, and it may be beneficial to consult with a qualified statistician in this respect.

The limitations of the applicability of any database should also be considered when designing a sampling strategy, along with any limitations or sample types unsuitable for assessment. For example, a database comprised solely of fish or seafood from Malta cannot be used to assess fish or seafood from other geographic origins. Ideally, comparisons against fish and seafood produced in the same year will give the highest confidence in the results.

Additionally, sampling should cover a range of variables, including different seasons, production methods (wild-caught versus farmed), and varying sizes and ages of fish. This comprehensive approach will help in creating a more versatile and reliable database. Proper documentation and traceability of each sample, including detailed metadata such as location, date, and method of capture or production, are crucial for ensuring the integrity and usefulness of the database.

The composition of fish may vary significantly depending on age, sex, environment and season. Fish and seafood from the exact geographic origin may also vary significantly yearly for similar reasons. Thus, for the database to be representative, seasonality and potential year-to-year variability must be taken into account when taking reference samples of fish and seafood.

4.1 Integrity of sampling

The process of taking fish and seafood for use as reference samples is critical to the integrity of any authenticity database.

Given the complexities involved, the same sampling procedure may not be possible to implement/achieve for fish and seafood collected throughout their supply chain. A range of sampling approaches will be needed to collect fish and seafood reference samples from all points in the supply chain prior to packing them into retail units, e.g., containers.

It is important to gain documented evidence that all personnel undertaking the above sampling activities are:

- Fully trained in the sampling procedures to be employed.
- Use a pre-defined documented sampling protocol.

It is equally important that all information being recorded for sampling is integral, fully traceable, and verifiable as being accurate. The following approaches to the recording of sampling activities and associated information (e.g., unique sample reference code or barcode) are considered essential and again ranked in the order of decreasing confidence:

- Sampling activity is fully recorded using digital technology (e.g., video/photo with linked time, date, and GPS data) and uploaded directly to blockchain software (i.e., an immutable record).
- Sampling activity is recorded in full using digital technology (e.g., video/photo with linked time, date, and GPS data) and held as metadata associated with the sample (no blockchain record).
- Sampling activity is captured using an independent audit/certification mechanism.

- Sampling activity is recorded as paper/electronic records only.
- Partial data is recorded, i.e., where only some of the required metadata, according to the scope of the database (as defined by the database owner), is available.
- No records are available.

This classification system allows open acknowledgement that most commercial authenticity databases are constructed with reference samples of varying confidence. It is considered best practice to use such information to interpret and report unknown samples for authenticity.

The above approach, or similar, should be considered as part of the quality assurance measures to ensure the validity of any authenticity database.

4.2 Sample traceability and associated metadata

Metadata relevance, scope, and availability are critical aspects of database verification, and they determine the integrity and robustness of any authentic database.

Traceability documentation and records

Complete traceability documentation and records from fisherman to the point of testing are essential when taking reference samples for inclusion in authenticity databases from any point in the fish and seafood supply chain before packing into retail units.

Due to the global sourcing of commercially traded fish and seafood, it is recognized that the possibilities and practicalities of collecting reference samples along all parts of the supply chain with full traceability may prove extremely difficult. Even if it were achieved, the associated cost would likely be prohibitive. Thus, recording relevant metadata such as sampling location using GPS data and the potential using Apps specifically designed to record remote sampling information may provide a cost-effective solution to this issue. Furthermore, the association of such Apps with blockchain technologies can offer immutable records of the metadata associated with fish and seafood reference samples taken.

Test data

Including test data relating to a fish or seafood reference sample in its associated metadata is beneficial. The scope of a database should determine the criteria for inclusion of a reference sample into a database. Where the scope of a database requires compliance with, for example, specific regulatory limits in the EU Regulations, then the relevant test data should be used to determine the acceptability of a reference sample.

Tests should ideally be performed using methods and laboratories accredited to ISO17025.

The fish and seafood supply chain

A generic sea-to-fork chain map for fish or seafood is presented in Figure 1. Two distinct supply chains can be recognized for global fish and seafood supply, 'direct (short) supply' and 'long supply.'

The **direct supply** chain (short supply chain) involves fishermen or aquaculture farms delivering seafood directly to local markets, restaurants, or consumers with minimal intermediaries, ensuring maximum freshness and traceability. This method often results in lower costs and higher quality due to the reduced time from harvest to consumption. The simplest example of 'direct supply' would involve a single fisherman or fish farm fishing fish or seafood from sea or aquaculture into retail units.

Figure 1. Generic sea-to-fork chain map for fish and seafood (adopted by Kresna et al., 2017)

In contrast, the **long supply** chain involves large-scale commercial fishing and industrial aquaculture, where seafood is extensively processed in factories before distribution to supermarkets, restaurants, and other retail outlets. This chain offers scalability, product variety, and strict quality control, albeit with more extended logistics and potential freshness reduction. Processing typically involves sorting, cleaning, gutting, filleting, portioning, and various preservation methods such as chilling, freezing, curing, or canning. The seafood is then packaged, labelled, and stored in cold storage before being shipped to the destination country, where it is distributed to markets or restaurants or further processed and packaged in retail units. Such supply chains can be long and complex. Both supply chains are essential, catering to different market needs and ensuring a steady seafood supply.

This supply chain map also illustrates where fish and seafood reference samples could be taken.

The points in the supply chain requiring consideration will vary depending on fish and seafood origin and supply chain complexity. These can be relatively simple, for example, from a single fisherman directly to the retail unit, or highly complex, involving multiple stages detailed below:

a) Fishing Vessels and Farms

Samples can be taken directly from the catch or harvested stock to check for contaminants, verify species, and perform an initial quality assessment.

b) Transportation

During transportation, especially for long hauls, samples may be taken to monitor temperature control and potential spoilage.

c) Processing facilities

Samples are taken at various stages of secondary processing (e.g., canning, smoking, freezing) to ensure the integrity and safety of the product. These operations are typically conducted in the country of origin.

d) Packaging

Sampling may occur, for example, from the filling line, warehouse storage, or after distribution at wholesale or retail sites (typically off-the-shelf).

e) Storage and Distribution

Sampling post-shipment could be conducted at the port of import or after transport to the packing factory or interim storage depot (in the country of importation). In cold storage facilities, regular sampling is conducted to monitor the environment and the seafood for any signs of spoilage or contamination during storage. At distribution centres, samples are taken to verify that the seafood has maintained its quality and safety throughout the distribution process.

f) Final product post-packing-factory processing (retail samples)

For retail fish and seafood samples included in the database as reference samples, the corresponding metadata associated with those samples must also be included, including all processing information associated with that particular sample lot, and each component of that particular fish and seafood batch must be traceable to the specific fisherman/fish farm (FAO, 2020).

4.3 Sampling fish and other seafood

Obtaining representative reference samples of the lot or batch of fish and seafood from which the samples were taken is critical for any authenticity database. This aim may be achieved by using the following:

- **Recognized statistical approaches:** This task requires random sampling of large numbers of barrels, containers, or boxes of fish or seafood.
- **Homogenizing:** The batch should be homogenized before sampling to ensure an even distribution of characteristics (this is particularly useful in batches with significant variability).
- **Random sampling** from a batch to avoid bias and ensure the sample represents the entire batch.
- **Cluster Sampling**, i.e., dividing the batch into clusters (e.g., bins or crates) and randomly selecting clusters for sampling, then sampling all items within the selected clusters.
- **Composite Sampling:** Combining multiple individual samples into a composite sample to average out local variations and provide a more accurate overall representation.
- **Representative Size.** I.e., ensuring the sample size is large enough to represent the entire batch statistically. A larger sample size reduces the margin of error and provides a more accurate reflection.
- It is considered unnecessary to take replicate samples for testing. Single-sample testing is considered fit-for-purpose.
- Samples should be collected in clean food-grade opaque glass, or preferably plastic, containers labelled with a unique sample identification code or number.
- **Temperature Control:** Maintain appropriate temperature conditions to preserve the integrity of the samples, especially if they are to be tested for freshness or microbiological content.
- Samples must be sealed, or bagged and sealed, with tamper-evident closures as part of the sampling process, and this requirement should be included in the pre-defined sampling protocol. Store samples in conditions that prevent spoilage or contamination, such as refrigeration or freezing, until analysis can be performed.
- **Documentation:** Maintain detailed records of the sampling process, including date, time, location, conditions, and any observations made during sampling. This task ensures traceability and accountability.

4.4 Sample integrity during transport and storage

The handling that the fish receive on land during pre-processing and processing will determine the quality of the final product. Seafood, known for its perishable nature, demands a specific environment throughout its journey to preserve its freshness. Maintaining the right temperature, humidity, and conditions during transit is paramount to ensuring its quality.

Chilling can effectively reduce spoilage of fish or seafood if done quickly and if the fish are kept chilled and handled carefully and hygienically. Immediate chilling of fish ensures high-quality products. The goal is to cool the fish as quickly as possible to as low a temperature as possible without freezing. However, chilling cannot prevent spoilage entirely, but in general, the colder the fish, the more significant the reduction in bacterial and enzyme activity.

Icing is widely employed for the chilled storage of freshwater fish. The dressed and cleaned fish is kept in a chill store in insulated boxes with proper icing before pre-processing. The advantage of using icing is that ice has a high latent heat of fusion, so it can remove a significant amount of heat as it melts without changing the temperature (0 °C; [Ninan, 2018](#)). Table 2 lists some of the advantages and disadvantages of the two methods.

Table 2. Advantages and disadvantages of chilling and freezing (Shawyer et al., 2003)

Chilling	Freezing
Short-term storage (up to one-month maximum for some species, only a few days for others)	Long-term storage (a year or more for some species)
Storage temperature 0 °C	Storage temperature well below zero, e.g. -30 °C
Relatively cheap	Relatively costly
The product resembles fresh fish	If poorly done, it can negatively impact the quality
Relatively low-tech	Relatively high tech
Low skills required	High skills required
Portable refrigeration	Generally static operations

Ensuring the integrity of fish and seafood during transport and storage is critical to maintaining their quality, safety, and freshness. This process involves maintaining a continuous cold chain, typically between 0 °C and 4 °C for fresh products and at -25 °C or lower for frozen products, using refrigerated vehicles and storage units with reliable temperature control systems. Proper packaging, such as insulated containers, cool boxes, vacuum sealing, and modified atmosphere packaging, helps preserve freshness and prevent spoilage. Efficient logistics, including rapid loading and unloading and humidity control in storage, further protect the products. Implementing traceability systems with barcoding ensures accurate tracking of conditions throughout the supply chain. Adherence to regulatory standards and regular audits verify compliance and identify areas for improvement. These measures collectively ensure that fish and seafood reach consumers in the best possible condition, maintaining their integrity from harvest to table ([Shawyer et al., 2003](#)).

Higher relative humidity may be permitted for frozen goods because the low temperatures mean microbial growth is no longer possible. Relative humidity in the hold/container should be kept at 95% to prevent drying out (freezer burn), an effect which may also be counteracted by plastic film packaging.

After testing, it is strongly recommended that all fish and seafood reference samples be stored frozen (-18 °C or lower) to maintain their integrity.

If a fish or seafood reference sample is to be stored for potential additional future testing, a record of sample storage history must be maintained.

4.5 Handling of samples on arrival at the test laboratory

Handling fish samples on arrival at the test laboratory is critical to ensure the integrity and accuracy of subsequent analyses. Proper handling techniques are essential to prevent contamination degradation and maintain the sample's original characteristics.

Here are the key steps involved:

- **Sample Logging:** Immediately upon arrival, record each sample in a logbook or electronic system. Details should include the date and time of arrival, sample identification number, source, and any pertinent collection information.
- **Temperature Recording:** Measure and record the temperature of the samples upon arrival to ensure they have been kept within the required range during transport.
- **Accurate Labelling:** Ensure that each sample is clearly labelled with a unique identifier that matches the information recorded during logging. Labels should include details such as sample ID, date, and type of analysis required.
- **Appropriate Storage Conditions:** Samples must be stored in conditions that preserve their integrity until analysis. Fresh fish samples typically require refrigeration at 0-4 °C, while frozen samples should be kept at -18 °C or lower. Store samples separately to prevent cross-contamination, especially if they are intended for different types of analyses (e.g., microbiological vs. chemical testing).
- **Preparation for Analysis:**
 - Sample Homogenization: For some tests, samples may need to be homogenized to ensure uniformity. After freeze-drying, the fish muscle tissue should be ground to a fine and uniform powder. The powder must be uniform to ensure homogeneity of the sample. This task can be challenging given the fibrous nature of muscle; therefore, one must grind the tissue as much as possible. If the sample is not homogenous, avoid using the fibrous pieces in the analysis, i.e. try to retrieve the finely grounded material for the analysis.
 - Inspection: Inspect the samples for any signs of spoilage, contamination, or damage.
 - Documentation: Ensure all steps taken upon arrival are documented, including any anomalies or actions taken regarding compromised samples ([Field Sampling of Fish, 2022](#)).

Any fish or seafood reference samples received at a testing laboratory showing visible container damage where contents may have been compromised should be discarded.

5 Analytical methods

This chapter deals with the analytical methods needed to determine the stable isotope composition of light elements and elemental composition of fish, gills and mussels. Several standardized analytical techniques are officially recognized, especially for determining food authenticity and traceability. These methods include instructions for sample preparation procedure(s) (e.g., washing, drying, grinding, filtering, weighing, extraction, equilibration, precipitation, digestion) and necessary analytical reagents together with the type(s) and model(s) of the instrument(s) needed for analysis. However, it should be noted that for every matrix (such as fish and mussels), the methods must be optimized and validated to provide comparable and robust results.

The power of stable isotope and elemental approach relies on having a unified database of authentic samples of sufficient numbers with which a 'suspect' test sample can be compared. Also, authentic samples must be statistically 'screened' to identify the key tracers that discriminate

between different types of plants, regions or countries of interest and farming practices. Ensuring that all stable isotope measurements are metrologically sound, for example, improving the quality of datasets and model evaluation by incorporating measurement uncertainty and, more generally, having the necessary metrological support, is vital, including official, standardized methods, appropriate reference materials (RMs), data handling, evaluation of measurement uncertainty and participation in interlaboratory comparisons. A part of this support is the availability of suitable RMs that allow the analyst to follow the “principle of identical treatment” and enable users to normalize measurements of samples to isotope–delta scales.

It is important to provide information on how the measurement results were normalized to a stable isotope scale (Skrzypek, 2013) by either providing the measurement model equation or describing the basic principles used (e.g., linear ordinary least squares regression and quadratic errors-in-variables regression). All other corrections applied to instrumental readings should include corrections for blanks, memory effects, drift, linearity/mass effects, isobaric effects, and other interferences.

All measurements are subject to uncertainty, which must be presented with the results. Simple uncertainty evaluations can be obtained from the standard deviation of a stated number of replicate analyses of a sample or matrix-matched RM. However, more comprehensive methods exist for evaluating uncertainty (e.g., GUM Gauss’s, Monte Carlo, Bayesian or Kragten methods) that capture additional contributions arising from the various corrections applied to the measurements. In addition, uncertainty can be evaluated from inter-laboratory comparisons.

The guidelines for stable isotope mass spectrometry have been provided by FIRMS (Dunn & Carter, 2018) and lately in the paper by Skrzypek et al. (2022) published as IUPAC Technical Report.

This deliverable provides information on how stable isotope and elemental analysis were performed within the FishEUTrust project to establish an appropriate traceability system for seafood.

5.1 Sampling

For FishEUTrust, the samples were provided by the CLLs (CETGA, IPMA and ABT) using the protocol described in *Chapter 4: Sampling Strategy*.

During a two-year study (between the summer of 2023 and the spring of 2024), 215 samples of fish and mussels were collected from two different locations: the Mediterranean Sea (Malta) and the Atlantic Ocean (Portugal and Spain). The sample (Table 3) consisted of aquaculture Seabass and Seabream, wild Seabream and mussels. In addition, four Slovenian commercial aquaculture fish samples and four from Croatia were collected. Commercial and Spanish aquaculture fish fillets and gills from the same sample were compared using stable isotope and multi-elemental analysis.

Table 3. The list of samples analyzed by the developed FishEUTrust protocol

Year			Mediterranean Sea (Malta)	Atlantic Ocean (Portugal)	Atlantic Ocean (Spain)	Total
2023 -2024	fillet	aquaculture seabass	30	/	/	30
	fillet	aquaculture seabream	/	30	15	45
	fillet	wild seabream	30	30	20	80
	edible part	aquaculture mussel	/	30	/	30
	edible part	wild mussel	/	30	/	30
						215
2024			Adriatic Sea (Slovenia)	Adriatic Sea (Croatia)		Total
	fillet	aquaculture seabass	2	2		4
	fillet	aquaculture seabream	2	2		4
					8	

2024			Adriatic Sea (Slovenia)	Adriatic Sea (Croatia)	Atlantic Ocean (Spain)	Total
	gills	aquaculture seabass	2	2		4
	gills	aquaculture seabream	2	2	15	19
						23

5.2 Sample preparation

Fish were first dissected, and the obtained fish fillets were frozen at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 hours. After 24 hr, fillets were thawed, and water extracted from fish fillet was filtered through a GF/PVDF 45/25 filter (Macherey-Nagel, Chromofil, Germany) and stored at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until analysis (but no more than 24 h). Furthermore, fish fillets were homogenized in a knife mill blender (Retsch) and freeze-dried (Liof Gamma 1-16 LSC plus, Christ, Germany) before further analysis. Notably, fish samples are not washed with MQ water to preserve the oxygen isotopic ratio ($^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$) in the water squeezed from the fillet.

5.3 Stable isotope analysis

The detailed protocol for determination of stable isotope composition in fish fillets, gills and edible parts of mussels is shown in Figures 2 and 3, respectively.

* The extracted water is compressed over a sterile gauze, filtered through a GF/PVDF 45/25 filter and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until analysis or measured immediately.

** Fillet fraction is homogenized three times with a 30 mL mixture of petroleum ether and diethyl ether (PeET:Et₂O) in a ratio 2:1, with Ultraturax (1200rpm x 3 min).

*** Fillet fraction is centrifuged three times in a 30 mL mixture of petroleum ether and diethyl ether (PeET:Et₂O) in a ratio of 2:1, using a centrifuge (3000 rpm x 5 min) to separate the fatty and defatted fraction of fillets.

**** Fillet fraction is cleaned by washing twice with 20 mL of Milli-Q water, using a centrifuge (3000 rpm x 3 min).

***** For CNS analysis in fillets and gills, 3.5 mg of sample was used. Recommended standards for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ are: USGS91, USGS89, USGS88, USGS43, IAEA600.

Figure 2. Protocol for determination of stable isotope composition in fish fillets and gills

* Mussel edible part fraction is homogenized three times with a 4 mL mixture of petroleum ether and diethyl ether (PeET:Et₂O) in a ratio of 2:1, with Ultraturax (1200rpm x 3 min).

** The mussel edible part is centrifuged three times in a 4 mL mixture of petroleum ether and diethyl ether (PeET:Et₂O) in a ratio of 2:1, using a centrifuge (3000 rpm x 5 min) to separate the fatty and defatted fraction.

*** Mussel edible part fraction is cleaned by washing twice in 3 mL of Milli-Q water, using a centrifuge (3000 rpm x 3 min).

**** For CNS analysis in the edible part of mussels, 3.5 mg of the sample was placed into a tin capsule. Recommended standards for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ are: USGS91, USGS89, USGS88, USGS43, IAEA600.

Figure 3. Protocol for determination of stable isotope composition in mussels

5.3.1 Determination of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in fish sample water

The determination of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values was performed on extracted water samples from the fish fillets. The method involves purging 200 μL of the sample with CO_2 . Once equilibrated, the oxygen isotopic composition was measured using an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS, IsoPrime 100, IsoPrime, Cheadle, UK), connected to a Multiflow Bio preparation system (Multi-Flow; IsoPrime, Cheadle, UK). Results were normalised against two laboratory reference materials seawater ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = +0.36 \pm 0.04 \text{ ‰}$) and snow ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = -18.91 \pm 0.03 \text{ ‰}$) and USGS53 ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = +5.47 \pm 0.03 \text{ ‰}$). Milli-Q water ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = -9.12 \pm 0.04 \text{ ‰}$) was used as laboratory reference material for independent control. The combined uncertainty for measurements of ^{18}O in water was $\pm 0.3 \text{ ‰}$, while the expanded uncertainty was $\pm 0.5 \text{ ‰}$.

5.3.2 Determination of the isotopic composition of bulk C, N and S in fish and mussel samples

Since defatting is recommended for samples subject to $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ analysis, stable isotope ratios of $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$, $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ and $^{34}\text{S}/^{32}\text{S}$ were measured in the defatted fish fillets or mussel edible parts. Approximately 4 g of lyophilized fish fillet or 0.4 g of lyophilized mussel edible part was extracted three times with a mixture of petrol ether (CARLO ERBA, Val-de-Reuill, Loop, France) and diethyl ether (Supelco, Merck, Germany), (2:1). 30 mL of the mixture was used with fish samples and 2.5 mL with the mussel samples. This step was followed by homogenization with an Ultraturax device (IKA® T18 digital ULTRA TURRAX®, Staufen, Germany) and centrifugation (Type Centric 322A, TEHTNICA, Slovenia) (5 min x 3000 rpm) to separate the solvent from the residue. The defatted fish fillets or edible parts of mussels were additionally washed two times with MiliQ water (20 mL in the case of fish samples and 0.3 mL in the case of mussels) and centrifuged (3 min x 3000 rpm) to separate the water. The defatted fraction was lyophilized, homogenized and saved at room temperature until analysis.

$\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values in defatted fish and mussels were determined by an IsoPrime100 – Vario PYRO Cube (OH/CNS Pyrolyser/Elemental Analyzer) (IsoPrime, Cheadle, Hulme, UK). Approximately 3.5 mg of the sample was put directly into a tin capsule, and the same amount of WO_3 was added. The tin capsule was sealed using tweezers and put into the automatic sampler of the elemental analyzer. The results for carbon and nitrogen were normalized against the following international reference materials: USGS89 with $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -18.13 \pm 0.11 \text{‰}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N} = +6.25 \pm 0.12 \text{‰}$, IAEA-600 with $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -27.73 \pm 0.04 \text{‰}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N} = +1.02 \pm 0.04 \text{‰}$, USGS88 with $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -16.06 \pm 0.07 \text{‰}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N} = +14.96 \pm 0.14 \text{‰}$, USGS91 with $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -28.28 \pm 0.08 \text{‰}$ and USGS43 with $\delta^{15}\text{N} = +8.44 \pm 0.10 \text{‰}$. While the results for sulfur were normalized against the international reference materials USGS89 with $\delta^{34}\text{S} = +3.86 \pm 0.56 \text{‰}$, USGS88 with $\delta^{34}\text{S} = +17.10 \pm 0.44 \text{‰}$, and USGS43 with $\delta^{34}\text{S} = +10.46 \pm 0.25 \text{‰}$. As control material, laboratory reference material CRP-IAEA casein with $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -20.3 \pm 0.09 \text{‰}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N} = +5.62 \pm 0.19 \text{‰}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S} = +4.18 \pm 0.74 \text{‰}$ was used. The reproducibility of measurements for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ was $\pm 0.2 \text{‰}$ and $\pm 0.7 \text{‰}$ for $\delta^{34}\text{S}$.

5.4 Multi-elemental analysis using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry

The detailed protocol for determining elemental composition in fish fillets, gills and edible parts of mussels is presented in Figure 4.

* = In each list, include a control material and a blank

** = Microwave program (ULTRAWAVE): Temperature ramp up to 240°C in 20 minutes, keep 240°C in 15 minutes. Recommended control materials: DOLT-5 Dogfish Liver, DORM-5 Fish Protein

Figure 4. Protocol for determination of elemental composition in fish fillets, gills and mussels

A known weight of lyophilized fish or mussel sample (≈ 0.1 g) was transferred to a pre-cleaned Teflon digestion vial, where 2 mL of 65 % HNO_3 (Merck, Germany, suprapur) was added. All the samples were digested using the ULTRAWAVE, Single Reaction Chamber (SRC) Microwave Digestion System (MILESTONE, Italy). The program was as follows: heating to 240 °C in 20 mins and held for 15 min at max 100 bar and max power: 1500 W. Digested solutions were transferred into measuring tubes and diluted to 10 mL using Milli-Q water. For quality control, blank samples and certified reference materials produced by the National Research Council of Canada (NRC): DOLT-5 Dogfish Liver and DORM-5 Fish Protein, were analyzed within the same batch as the samples. At least every tenth sample was prepared in two parallels. Before analysis, samples were diluted with 5% HNO_3 in a ratio of 1:5. Selected elements (Li, B, Na, Mg, P, S, K, Ca, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Rb, Sr, Mo, Ag, Cd, Sn, Sb, Ba, Hg, Tl, Pb, U) were determined using an Agilent 8800 triple quadrupole inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer, QQQ-ICP-MS (Agilent, USA). Internal standards (Y, Rh, Sc, and Gd) were added online in all modes, and external calibration was used for quantification.

Limits of detection were calculated based on three standard deviations of blank measurements and were for Li (30.0 ng/g), B (0.28 $\mu\text{g/g}$), Na (0.003 mg/g), Mg (0.0003 mg/g), P (0.0006 mg/g), S (0.23 mg/g), K (0.0057 mg/g), Ca (0.0077 mg/g), V (0.6 ng/g), Cr (15.0 ng/g), Mn (0.007 $\mu\text{g/g}$), Fe (0.09 $\mu\text{g/g}$), Co (0.9 ng/g), Ni (40 ng/g), Cu (0.02 $\mu\text{g/g}$), Zn (0.2 $\mu\text{g/g}$), As (0.005 $\mu\text{g/g}$), Se (0.008 $\mu\text{g/g}$), Rb (0.0025 $\mu\text{g/g}$), Sr (0.02 $\mu\text{g/g}$), Mo (1.0 ng/g), Ag (1.0 ng/g), Cd (0.6 ng/g), Sn (2.0 ng/g), Sb (0.7 ng/g), Ba (3.0 ng/g), Hg (0.002 $\mu\text{g/g}$), Tl (0.4 ng/g), Pb (2.0 ng/g), U (0.2 ng/g).

6 IsoFoodTrack database

The traceability system based on isotopic and elemental composition relies on databases of authentic reference samples that are sufficient to capture the range of values for authentic food products from any given location. These need to take into account variations in farming and husbandry practice as well as climatic and environmental variations. Databases also need to be curated and kept up to date. Building a database and keeping it up to date is a considerable task, given the amount of variation that needs to be included. The European Commission has maintained an isotopic database for wine for over 20 years that could be used for geographic origin interpretation (Christoph et al., 2015). Other databases are much less developed. There are some freely available European databases, such as the EU wine database, but many databases are generally not shared partly because of intellectual property issues and because different authentic sample pre-treatment may have been used in their development. The database SIRA is already being used for well-defined products, such as Parma ham, Grana Padano Cheese and Parmigiano Reggiano cheese in Italy (Camin et al., 2017).

At the Jožef Stefan Institute, the IsoFoodTrack database (www.isofoodtrack.ijs.si) was developed for different commodities of interest, such as spices, milk and dairy products, oils, and meat. The FishEU Trust project provides an excellent opportunity to upgrade the database to establish an appropriate traceability system for seafood.

The IsoFoodTrack database framework can be used to organize the data collected and other activities, enabling further processing of the data by statistical methods, GIS applications and modelling. The steps involved in constructing the database can be divided into the following three phases:

- Phase I, the structure of the database, was defined. The protocol for data preparation was evolved to minimize the labour involved in filling the database.
- Phase II, this phase meant filling the database with data gained during the project evolution.
- Phase III, the tasks here were dedicated to developing routines/queries for extracting data from the database.

The structure of the database

The database's structure was defined according to the defined gaps and requirements for the traceability system. When specifying requirements for any database, many conditions must be considered. Presently, tools are commercially available, providing starting points for database creation so that database builders do not have to consider all basic requirements. Leveraging such tools allows researchers to focus on the specific design of the database.

The fundamental requirements of IsoFoodTrack included (i) the underlying database and (ii) the application layer.

Underlying database

The following points were considered in the underlying database:

- The storage medium used for the underlying database is PostgreSQL.
- The structure of a similar database was investigated according to the partner's involvement in different projects, such as TRACE and FoodIntegrity and the categories presented in Figure 5.
- The underlying database schema is flexible to mitigate the need for database builders to modify the schema to accommodate growing metadata or requirements for analytical results.

andName/Spec	Sampling date	Source	Country	Latitude		Longitude		Distance from the coast	Altitude	Annual mean temperature	Annual mean precipitation	$\delta^2\text{H}$	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$	$\delta^{15}\text{N}$	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	$\delta^{34}\text{S}$	
				y coordinate (WGS 84)	x coordinate (WGS 84)	km	m										°C
Sea bream		aquaculture	Malta	35°50'10.9"N	14°32'40.8"E			0									
Sea bream		aquaculture	Malta	35°50'10.9"N	14°32'40.8"E												
Sea bream		wild	Malta	35°49'18.8"N	14°34'29.5"E												
Sea bream		wild	Malta	35°49'18.8"N	14°34'29.5"E												
Sea bream		wild	Spain	42°31'11.5"N	9°02'14.1"W												
Sea bream		wild	Spain	42°31'11.5"N	9°02'14.1"W												
Sea bream		aquaculture	Portugal	37°02'01.9"N	7°49'05.1"W												
Sea bream		aquaculture	Portugal	37°02'01.9"N	7°49'05.1"W												
Sea bream		wild	Portugal	36°59'24.9"N	7°49'47.9"W												
Sea bream		wild	Portugal	36°59'24.9"N	7°49'47.9"W												

Figure 5. Example of the structure of the database in Excel with selected categories

Application layer

The application provides an interface between the database and the user and streamlines the process of working with the database. The IsoFoodTrack database interface is presented in Figure 6.

Commodities: Choose View: Map Table

IsoFoodTrack: Database for Food Authenticity and Traceability

Oils Milk & Dairy Meat Spices Truffles Seafood Cereals

IsoFood TRACK

Food authenticity and traceability testing, essential for ensuring food safety and integrity, use techniques like stable isotopic analysis to detect fraud, identify food origins, and determine production methods.

IsoFoodTrack, a key resource in this field, provides a comprehensive database of isotopic, elemental composition and other data along with detailed metadata on commonly adulterated foods, aiding in the accurate verification of their authenticity and geographical origin.

IJS PROMEDLIFE FishEU Trust FSE-COOP METM FOOD anrs PRIMA ariafici

Figure 6. Interface of IsoFoodTrack database

The following aspects were considered for the application:

- Security, Logins, Permissions, Auditing (created, updated) – Currently, the database is not publicly accessible, and it is only available to the project partners to validate it. In the future, when all the data is published, the database will be made available to different stakeholders.
- The configuration or metadata and results, such as Column Name, Data Type, Units, Validation and Categorization, are included in the database. The structure is presented in Figure 7.
- The database supports importing data from Excel and exporting data in the same format.
- When results that will be included in the database are submitted, they are not automatically available but are reviewed by the administrator and isotope expert.
- Users and administrators of the database are not accessing the underlying database directly (for data access or schema changes). The data are accessible throughout an application layer.
- The application layer retrieves the data through a web application (database interface).
- The data can be read easily through the application layer.

The screenshot shows a web interface for a database. At the top, there is a search bar labeled 'Commodities:' with 'Seafood' entered. To the right, there are options to 'View:' as a 'Map' or a 'Table'. Below this is a 'Filter' section with various input fields for 'Species', 'Type', 'Date', 'CC', 'L', 'Lat.', 'Lon.', 'Altit.', 'Temp.', 'Prec.', and 'isotope'. A 'View' section is also present. The main part of the screenshot is a table with the following structure:

Species	Type	Date	CC	L	Lat. WGS 84	Lon. WGS 84	Altit. m	Temp. °C	Prec. mm	$\delta^{2}\text{H}$ ‰	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ‰	$\delta^{15}\text{N}$ ‰	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ‰	$\delta^{34}\text{S}$ ‰
Seafood	Patinopecten	N/A	Chin	E	39.8283	119.4119	0	14.04	109.65	N/A	-20.30	7.40	N/A	N/A
Seafood	Patinopecten	N/A	Chin	E	39.8283	119.4119	0	14.04	109.65	N/A	-20.20	7.40	N/A	N/A
Seafood	Patinopecten	N/A	Chin	E	39.8283	119.4119	0	14.04	109.65	N/A	-20.40	7.50	N/A	N/A
Seafood	Patinopecten	N/A	Chin	E	39.8283	119.4119	0	14.04	109.65	N/A	-20.00	7.50	N/A	N/A
Seafood	Patinopecten	N/A	Chin	E	39.8283	119.4119	0	14.04	109.65	N/A	-19.90	7.30	N/A	N/A
Seafood	Patinopecten	N/A	Chin	E	39.8283	119.4119	0	14.04	109.65	N/A	-19.60	7.30	N/A	N/A

Figure 7. The structure of the database

A central dedicated repository is www.isofoodtrack.ijs.si, created to store analytical data relating to food authenticity. It is envisioned that it will act as a source for isotope data relating to food authenticity that can be easily connected to other currently developed databases such as FoodIntegrity, FNS-Cloud or METROFOOD-RI and will be open access.

To make the integration between the datasets with minimal effort, we propose a formal representation of the isotopic knowledge in food research and identify the requirements for such representation. We have respected the opinion recently published by [Pauli et al. \(2017\)](#), where the authors explain why a centralized repository for isotopic data is required and provide a shared vision for IsoBank that would offer a viable and powerful framework to organize, consolidate, and share stable isotope data across disciplines. In Figure 8, meta-data and provenance data are presented for describing the measurement of isotopes in food/drink items.

The established database was further used for different applications, including visualization and statistical modelling, as a part of the FishEUTrust application.

Figure 8. A schematic of the proposed database structure outlining how contributors and users would interface with samples, analyses, measurements, and datasets to describe stable isotope data.

7 Real-life application performed in FishEUTrust

Quality assurance controls were built into the study design. These were adopted to ensure the appropriate number of samples had been taken, test the analytical and interpretative methodology, challenge the database, and help judge the confidence level that could be placed on the SIRA results. The samples were analyzed using the analytical methods presented in Chapter 5: Analytical Methods and included in the IsoFoodTrack database for further evaluation.

7.1 Data visualization

The IsoFoodTrack database provides a data visualization tool in a graphical mode (maps) that enables the users to see and understand trends, outliers, and patterns in the dataset. An example of a visualization tool in a graphical mode is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Graphical presentation (google map) of stable isotope data of light elements on fish and mussels from CLL

7.2 Statistical evaluation of the data and modelling

The statistical evaluation of results and the development of models are guided by the specific question we want to address. Three general chemometric approaches exist: (1) explorative analysis, (2) classification, and (3) calibration. All three are used in food science, but the chosen method should align with the objectives of the question posed, ensuring that the analysis is both relevant and effective in providing meaningful insights. This chapter presents various examples relevant to evaluating the results. The main question was related to the differentiation of the samples related to production (wild vs. farmed) and geographical discrimination.

Statistical methods

The final elemental data were prepared in Microsoft Excel. The statistical calculations were performed using the XLSTAT software package (Addinsoft, New York, USA). Simple statistical analyses were conducted using the Mann-Whitney test since the data are not normally distributed.

For data analyses, different statistical procedures were used, including nonparametric Mann-Whitney test, linear discriminant analysis (LDA), orthogonal partial least squares discriminant analysis (OPLS-DA) and data-driven soft independent modelling of class analogy (DD-SIMCA). Linear discriminant analysis is one of the simplest classifiers, albeit to compute a centroid for each class, and the pooled variance-covariance matrix requires a sufficient ratio (≥ 3) between the number of samples and the number of variables. Also, LDA cannot cope with highly collinear data, which is common in chemical problems (Marini, 2009). The LDA test was done using the XLSTAT software package (Addinsoft, New York, USA).

Other techniques – in particular, orthogonal partial least squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) have been devised to overcome these limitations. The resulting model is a linear model proven statistically equivalent to the solution obtained by LDA. Due to its latent vector-based technique, problems like a minimum sample-to-variable ratio and the absence of collinearity can be overcome (Marini, 2009). Alternatively, orthogonal partial least squares discriminant analysis (OPLS-DA) is a modification of the PLS-DA method, which improves interpretability by filtering out any variation not related to the discriminating response by separating that part of the variance used for predictive purposes from the non-predictive variance, which is then made orthogonal. The prediction performance of the OPLS-DA model was evaluated via sensitivity (true positives) and specificity (true negatives), calculated as described by Fiamegos et al. (2021). The model's accuracy $(TP+TN)/(TP+FP+FN+TN)$ was calculated where TP is a true positive, TN a true negative, FP a false positive, and FN a false negative. Accuracy is the ratio of correctly labelled subjects (samples) to the whole subject (sample) pool. Candidates for discriminant markers were selected based on a variable's importance in the projection (VIP) values of the OPLS-DA models, where a value higher than one was considered the threshold. OPLS-DA were obtained using SIMCA-P (version 17, Sartorius Stedim Biotech, Umea, Sweden).

A modification of the SIMCA method called data-driven SIMCA or DD-SIMCA (Pomerantsev & Rodionova, 2014) was then used as a one-class classifier (OCC) technique. DD-SIMCA consists of two steps: (1) principal component analysis (PCA) is applied to the training dataset, and (2) for each object from the training set, two distances are calculated: the score distance (SD) and the orthogonal distance (OD), and the corresponding critical limits. The SD represents the position of a sample within the score space, while the OD is the orthogonal Euclidean distance of the sample to the score space. DD-SIMCA adds the possibility of estimating the data-driven distribution parameters, making an acceptance area/decision rule for a given value possible.

The classification results are described as 'sensitivity' and 'specificity' or in standard statistical terms such as type I error (α) and type II error (β). When alternative classes are presented, the β -error can be calculated for a given α -error as described by Pomerantsev & Rodionova (2014). The sensitivity denotes a share of correctly identified samples of the target class, while specificity is a portion of objects of an alternative class correctly identified as members of that alternative class. The

sensitivity can be defined as $100(1-\alpha)\%$ and specificity as $100(1-\beta)\%$ (Fidelis et al., 2017; Rodionova et al., 2016). DD-SIMCA calculations were performed in RStudio using the DD-SIMCA MATLAB GUI tool (Zontov et al., 2017) and the mdatools package for R 4.0.3 (Kucheryavskiy, 2020).

Wild vs. farmed

The first evaluation of results involved comparing two isotopic compositions using a bi-plot. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ are linked to feeding habits and the trophic position, respectively. Wild marine fish tissues usually have higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values than farmed fish because the dissolved carbon pool of the natural diets of wild fish ($\delta^{13}\text{C}=0\text{‰}$) is enriched in ^{13}C than the atmospheric carbon (CO_2) used for photosynthesis by terrestrial plants. As for nitrogen isotopes, fish occupying higher trophic levels have higher $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values (Camin et al., 2017), even if these values can be influenced by other factors, such as maturity or growth rate, seasonal isotopic variations in coastal marine environments, and possible spoilage of the fish sample between collection and analysis. The results show that both $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ are higher in wild specimens compared to the farmed ones (Figure 10). These results are in accordance to what has been previously reported in literature: studies based on determination of isotopes abundances of C and N successfully led to the discrimination between wild and farmed gilthead sea bream (Morrison et al., 2007; Serrano et al., 2007), shrimps (Gamboa-Delgado et al., 2014; Ortea and Gallardo, 2015), Atlantic salmon (Dempson and Power, 2004), and sea bass (Bell et al., 2007). In the present study, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values also discriminate sea bream according to geographical origins. Lower $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values have been observed in some Portuguese wild samples, indicating that these fish were likely caught in areas with higher terrestrial particulate matter. In addition, no statistical difference in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values was observed between wild and farmed fish from Malta, indicating possible mislabeling of wild fish samples.

Figure 10. Relationship between $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in farmed and wild fish fillets from different countries a) with Malta wild samples; b) without wild samples from Malta.

Further, OPLS-DA has been applied to classify samples by production method (wild vs farmed) regardless of their origin of production (Portugal, Spain, Malta, Slovenia, Croatia) using only stable isotopes (Figure 11). In this analysis, the wild samples from Malta were not included. Overall accuracy was 100%, with the most discriminant parameters $\delta^{34}\text{S} > \delta^{15}\text{N} > \delta^{13}\text{C} > \delta^{18}\text{O}$ exhibiting higher values in wild fish. These results indicate that elemental composition is unnecessary when discriminating fish based on production type. However, it should be noted that these findings are only preliminary, and to develop a more robust model, additional data from various countries need to be included.

Figure 11. OPLS-DA (SIMCA): differentiation of fish samples based on production type (farmed vs wild) including only stable isotope variables in all countries (Malta wild samples were excluded).

Further, a statistical evaluation of mussels from Portugal was performed. The Man-Whitney test indicated that the most powerful differentiating markers between wild and farmed mussels are $\delta^{34}\text{S}$, P, Mo, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$. The boxplots of these parameters are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Box plots of the most powerful parameters responsible for differentiation between farmed and wild mussels

Figure 13. OPLS-DA score plots in the pairwise comparisons between different types of mussel production farmed vs wild. The ellipse on the score plot represents the 95% confidence interval.

Higher values of $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ concentrations of Mo were observed in wild species, while concentrations of P and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ were higher in farmed mussels. Higher concentrations of P are probably related to the feeding input enriched in P.

Further, OPLS-DA was applied to analyze the observed differences between different production types (Figure 13). Unfortunately, the separation using only stable isotope analysis was not satisfied (model accuracy: 72 %). Therefore, all variables were included in the model. The model was optimized, and the most promising variables to separate wild from farmed mussels were $\delta^{34}\text{S}$, P, Mo, Tl, K, As, Mg, Na, Zn, V, Rb, Cd, Cu, Pb, and Ag. The overall accuracy of the model was 85%.

Geographical origin

The first analysis was performed on fish gills and fillets. The Mann-Whitney test indicated a statistical difference in all isotopic and elemental parameters except for Se. Overall, the concentrations of elements in gills were higher for the following elements: P, Ca, Mn, Fe, Co, Pb, Zn, Sr, Mo, Ba, and Cd, compared to fillets indicating higher accumulation of these elements in gills. The objective of this evaluation was not related to the safety or quality of the fish; the primary goal was to demonstrate the effectiveness of using elemental and stable isotope composition as parameters to differentiate samples based on their origin.

The results show the effective gill and fillet samples according to geographical location using stable isotopes and linear discriminant analysis (LDA). This analysis included only samples from Spain, Slovenia, and Croatia. The model's accuracy was 100 % for gills and 95 % for fillets (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Discriminant function score plot for fish a) gills and b) fillet discriminating country of origin based on stable isotope data.

Further, using only stable isotope data, OPLS-DA could differentiate fish according to the country of production. When both production practices were included in the evaluation, the overall accuracy was 75% (Figure 15). In the case that only farmed fish were subject to evaluation, accuracy was 94%. In both cases, the most discriminate parameters are as follows: $\delta^{18}\text{O} > \delta^{13}\text{C} > \delta^{15}\text{N} > \delta^{34}\text{S}$.

Notably, lower isotopic values are, on average, lower in the Mediterranean region (Malta, Slovenia, Croatia) than in the Atlantic region (Portugal, Spain).

Figure 15. OPLS-DA score plots in comparisons between different countries of origin: a) the whole dataset with wild and farmed; b) only farmed samples. The ellipse on the score plot represents the 95% confidence interval.

The accuracy of the model based on the whole dataset, including farmed and wild fish, could be improved if all the data, including elements, were taken into account. A good separation of the fish samples based on the geographical location was obtained. The overall accuracy of the OPLS-DA model was 94%. The most powerful variables for differentiating fish samples from five different geographical locations are $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, K, P, Rb, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$, Mg, Zn, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, S, Co, Hg, and Se. Notably, all discriminating elements are statistically higher in the Atlantic than in the Mediterranean.

Figure 16. a) OPLS-DA score plots and b) VIP values in comparisons between different countries of origin for farmed and wild fish. The ellipse on the score plot represents the 95% confidence interval. The red dotted line indicates the criteria for identifying the variables, which is important for the developed model.

The final example involved verifying the declared origin of fish samples, i.e., whether the fish samples originate from a specific country, e.g., Portugal. Unlike discriminant methods, DD-SIMCA distinguishes objects of a particular class, i.e., the target class (authentic Portuguese samples), from all other objects and classes, referred to as alternative sets (non-Portuguese samples). In this case, information from the non-target samples was used only to evaluate the model's performance. The target set was randomly divided into a training set (70% of data from the primary dataset) and a test set (30% of data from the primary dataset) to assess the model's validity. This division roughly corresponds to 4-5-fold cross-validation and represents a good compromise between having sufficient data to build a good model from the test dataset.

Figure 17. DD-SIMCA classification model of a) authentic fish samples (green dots; $n = 55$) from Portugal (wild and farmed samples), b) fish samples (red dots; $n = 98$) from outside Portugal (wild and farmed samples from Spain, Malta, Slovenia, Croatia). The green line signifies the acceptance area at $\alpha = 0.05$.

An exploratory data analysis was performed using the entire dataset with selected variables to explore the data structure and analyze the figure of merit (FoM) results concerning the number of PCs. A classification model was then built using the target set, the alternative set (samples from abroad) and the PCA model with a selected number of PCs. Results are presented in Figure 17. Sensitivity and specificity were used as figures of merit obtained from the target and alternative set. Good sensitivity of the model (93%; 4 authentic samples, yellow dots, were misclassified) and excellent specificity of 98% (2 samples from abroad, blue dots representing Spanish wild samples, were misclassified) was obtained. The overall accuracy was 96%, and the most significant variables for discriminating between Portuguese and non-Portuguese fish samples were $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, Mg, P, S, K, and Se.

8 Conclusions

In conclusion, establishing a robust traceability system, including a fit-for-purpose database and implementing a standardized protocol for sampling and testing are essential steps in combating food fraud and ensuring consumer confidence in the authenticity and safety of food products, particularly in the fish and seafood industry.

In FishEUTrust, the developed protocol has been tested on wild and farmed fish and mussel samples from different countries (Malta, Portugal, Spain, Slovenia, and Croatia). The IsoFoodTrack database, a key component of the FishEUTrust project, serves as a centralized repository for storing and analyzing the extensive data generated. Utilizing advanced statistical analyses, including LDA, OPLS-DA, and DD-SIMCA, has enabled precise classification and discrimination of samples based on their production method and geographical origin. This study was also designed to gain experience using stable isotope ratio analysis (SIRA) in combination with elemental analysis as a screening tool to combat food misdescription. However, the robustness and applicability must be further investigated by upgrading the database with more samples from different countries. Additionally, recent advances in machine learning to classify food and explain the reasoning behind predictions will significantly improve data interpretation.

Future directions

The IsoFoodTrack database is envisioned as a central repository for analytical data related to food authenticity. Integration with other databases and initiatives is planned for broader access and utilization. Within the FishEUTrust project, the database will be combined with metagenomic and DNA barcoding techniques. Artificial intelligence will be used to evaluate these results and identify relevant biomarkers for verifying the type of production and country of origin, which will be economically and practically more applicable in seafood traceability systems. Furthermore, we plan to use IsoFoodTrack to digitize the SEAFOOD^{TOMORROW} benchmark and explore the potential of integrating the data into a developed blockchain/passport system (WP7).

9 References

- Bell, J. G., Preston, T., Henderson, R. J., Strachan, F., Bron, J. E., Cooper, K., & Morrison, D. J. (2007) Discrimination of Wild and Cultured European Sea Bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) Using Chemical and Isotopic Analyses. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 55(15), 5934–5941 <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0704561>
- Bianchini, G., Brombin, V., Carlino, P., Mistri, E., Natali, C., & Salani, G. M. (2021) Traceability and Authentication of Manila Clams from North-Western Adriatic Lagoons Using C and N Stable Isotope Analysis. *Molecules* 26(7), Article 7. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26071859>
- Camin, F., Boner, M., Bontempo, L., Fauhl-Hassek, C., Kelly, S.D., Riedl, J., Rossmann, A. (2017) Stable isotope techniques for verifying the declared geographical origin of food in legal cases. *Trends in Food Science and Technology* 61, 176-187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2016.12.007>
- Camin, F., Perini, M., Bontempo, L., Galeotti, M., Tibaldi, E., & Piasentier, E. (2018) Stable isotope ratios of H, C, O, N and S for the geographical traceability of Italian rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). *Food Chemistry* 267, 288–295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.06.017>
- Christoph, N., Hermann, A., Wachter, H. (2015) 25 Years authentication of wine with stable isotope analysis in the European Union – review and outlook. *BIO Web of Conferences*, 5, 02020.
- Danezis, G.P., Tsagkaris A.S., Camin F., Brusica V., Georgiou C.A. (2016) Food authentication: techniques, trends & emerging approaches. *Trends in Analytical Chemistry* 85, 123–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2016.02.026>
- del Rio-Lavín, A., Weber, J., Molkontin, J., Jiménez, E., Artetxe-Arrate, I., Pardo, M. Á. (2022) Stable isotope and trace element analysis for tracing the geographical origin of the Mediterranean mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) in food authentication. *Food Control* 139, 109069. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2022.109069>
- Dempson, J.B., Power, M. (2004) Use of stable isotopes to distinguish farmed from wild Atlantic salmon, *Salmo salar*. *Ecological Freshwater Fish* 13, 176–84.
- Donarski, J., Camin, F., Fauhl-Hassek, C., Posey, R., Sudnik, M. (2019) Sampling guidelines for building and curating food authenticity databases. *Trends in Food Science and Technology* 90, 187–193.
- Dong, X., Han, C., Li, L. (2022) Stable isotope ratio analysis for the authentication of sea urchin (*Mesocentrotus nudus*) from different culture areas in the North Yellow Sea, China. *Aquaculture* 561, 738637. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2022.738637>
- Drivelos, S. A., Georgiou, C. A. (2012) Multi-element and multi-isotope-ratio analysis to determine the geographical origin of foods in the European Union. *Trends in Analytical Chemistry* 40, 38–51.
- Dunn P.J.H., Carter, J.F. eds. (2018) Good practice guide for isotope ratio mass spectrometry, 2nd Edition. <https://www.forensic-isotopes.org/assets/FIRMS%20Good%20Practice%20Guide%20Second%20Edition.pdf>
- FAO (2020). The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2020. Sustainability in action. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca9229en>
- Fiamegos, Y., Dumitrascu, C., Papoci, S., de la Calle, M. B. (2021) Authentication of PDO paprika powder (Pimentón de la Vera) by multivariate analysis of the elemental fingerprint determined by ED-XRF. A feasibility study. *Food Control* 120, 107496. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2020.107496>
- Fidelis, M., Santos, J.S., Coelho, A.L.K., Rodionova, O.Y., Pomerantsev, A., Granato, D. (2017) Authentication of juices from antioxidant and chemical perspectives: A feasibility quality control study using chemometrics. *Food Control* 73, 796–805. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2016.09.043>
- Field Sampling of Fish for Disease Investigation and Health Monitoring. Guidelines and Procedures Manual. (2022) Centre for Aquatic Animal Health & Vaccines. *Department of Natural Resources and Environment Tasmania. Tasmanian Government*, 13 p.
- Gamboa-Delgado, J., Molina-Poveda, C., Godínez-Siardia, D.E., Villarreal-Cavazos, D., Ricque-Marie, D., Cruz-Suárez, L.E., Gillanders, B (2014) Application of stable isotope analysis to differentiate shrimp extracted by industrial fishing or produced through aquaculture practices. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Science* 71, 1520–8.
- Gong, Y., Li, Y., Chen, X., Chen, L. (2018) Potential use of stable isotope and fatty acid analyses for traceability of geographic origins of jumbo squid (*Dosidicus gigas*). *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry* 32(7), 583–589. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rcm.8071>
- Gopi, K., Mazumder, D., Sammut, J., Saintilan, N., Crawford, J., Gadd, P. (2019a) Combined use of stable isotope analysis and elemental profiling to determine provenance of black tiger prawns (*Penaeus monodon*). *Food Control* 95, 242–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2018.08.012>
- Gopi, K., Mazumder, D., Sammut, J., Saintilan, N., Crawford, J., Gadd, P. (2019b) Isotopic and elemental profiling to trace the geographic origins of farmed and wild-caught Asian seabass (*Lates calcarifer*). *Aquaculture* 502, 56–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2018.12.012>
- Han, C., Dong, S., Li, L., Gao, Q. (2021) Efficacy of using stable isotopes coupled with chemometrics to differentiate the production method and geographical origin of farmed salmonids. *Food Chemistry* 364, 130364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.130364>

- Kelly, S., Heaton, K., Hoogewerff, J. (2005) Tracing the geographical origin of food: the application of multi-element and multi-isotope analysis. *Trends in Food Science and Technology* 16, 555–567.
- Kim, H., Suresh Kumar, K., Shin, K.-H. (2015) Applicability of stable C and N isotope analysis in inferring the geographical origin and authentication of commercial fish (Mackerel, Yellow Croaker and Pollock). *Food Chemistry* 172, 523–527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.09.058>
- Kresna, B.A., Seminar, K.B., Marimin, M. (2017) Developing a Traceability System for Tuna Supply Chains. *International Journal of Supply Chain Management* 6(3), Article 3
- Kucheryavskiy, S. (2020) mdatools – R package for chemometrics. *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems* 198, 103937. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemolab.2020.103937>
- Luo, R., Jiang, T., Chen, X., Zheng, C., Liu, H., Yang, J. (2019) Determination of geographic origin of Chinese mitten crab (*Eriocheir sinensis*) using integrated stable isotope and multi-element analyses. *Food Chemistry* 274, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2018.08.104>
- Luykx, D.M.A.M., van Ruth, S.M. (2008) An overview of analytical methods for determining the geographical origin of food products. *Food Chemistry* 107, 897–911.
- Marini, F. (2009). *Classification Methods in Chemometrics*. *Current Analytical Chemistry* 6(1), 72–79. <https://doi.org/10.2174/157341110790069592>
- Martino, J.C., Mazumder, D., Gadd, P., Doubleday, Z.A. (2022) Tracking the provenance of octopus using isotopic and multi-elemental analysis. *Food Chemistry* 371, 131133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.131133>
- Mazarakioti, E.C., Zotos, A., Thomatou, A.A., Kontogeorgos, A., Patakas, A., Athanasios Ladavos, A. (2022) Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS), a Useful Tool in Authenticity of Agricultural Products' and Foods' Origin. *Foods* 11(22). doi: 10.3390/foods11223705.
- Molkentin, J., Lehmann, I., Ostermeyer, U., Rehbein, H. (2015) Traceability of organic fish – Authenticating the production origin of salmonids by chemical and isotopic analyses. *Food Control* 53, 55–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2015.01.003>
- Morrison, D.J., Preston, T., Bron, J.E., Hemderson, R.J., Cooper, K., Strachan, F., Bell, J.G. (2007) Authenticating production origin of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) by chemical and isotopic fingerprinting. *Lipids* 42, 537–45.
- Ni, X., Li, X., Ran, G., Chen, J., Jiang, X., Sun, J., Bai, W. (2022) Determination of the geographical origin of *Trachinotus ovatus* and *Pampus argenteus* in China by multi-element and stable isotope analysis. *Food Chemistry* 394, 133457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2022.133457>
- Ninan, G. (2018). Handling and Chilled Storage of Fish and Shell Fish. ICAR-Central Institute of Fisheries Technology. 20–26.
- Oliveira, E.J.V.M., Sant'Ana, L.S., Ducatti, C., Denadai, J.C., de Souza Kruliski, C.R. (2011) The use of stable isotopes for authentication of gadoid fish species. *European Food Research and Technology* 232(1), 97–101. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-010-1367-7>
- Ortea, I., Gallardo, J.M. (2015) Investigation of production method, geographical origin and species authentication in commercially relevant shrimps using stable isotope ratio and/or multi-element analyses combined with chemometrics: An exploratory analysis. *Food Chemistry* 170, 145–53.
- Pauli, J.N., Newsome, S.D., Cook, J.A., Harrod, C., Steffan, S.A., Baker, C.J, et al. (2017) Opinion: Why we need a centralized repository for isotopic data. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 114(12), 2997–3001.
- Pomerantsev, A.L., Rodionova, O.Y. (2014) Concept and role of extreme objects in PCA/SIMCA. *Journal of Chemometrics* 28(5), 429–438. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cem.2506>
- Reilly, A. (2018) Overview of food fraud in the fisheries sector. FAO. 32 p. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/20.500.14283/i8791en>
- Rodionova, O. Y., Titova, A.V., Pomerantsev, A.L. (2016) Discriminant analysis is an inappropriate method of authentication. *TrAC - Trends in Analytical Chemistry* 78, 17–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2016.01.010>
- Serrano, R., Blanes, M.A., Orero, L. (2007) Stable isotope determination in wild and farmed gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) tissues from the western Mediterranean. *Chemosphere* 69, 1075–80.
- Shawyer, M., Medina Pizzali, A.F. (2003) The use of ice on small fishing vessels. FAO Fisheries Technical Paper. No. 436. Rome, FAO, 108 p.
- Skrzypek, G. Normalization procedures and reference material selection in stable HCNOS isotope analyses: an overview. (2013) *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry* 405, 2815–2823. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-012-6517-2>
- Skrzypek, G., Colin, A., E., Böhlke, J.K., Bontempo, L., Brewer, P., Camin, F., Carter, J.F., Chartrand, M.M.G. et al. (2022) Minimum requirements for publishing hydrogen, carbon, nitrogen, oxygen and sulfur stable-isotope delta results (IUPAC Technical Report). *Pure and Applied Chemistry* 94, 1249–1255. <https://doi.org/10.1515/pac-2021-1108>
- Takizawa, Y., Takano, Y., Choi, B. et al. (2020). A new insight into isotopic fractionation associated with decarboxylation in organisms: implications for amino acid isotope approaches in biogeoscience. *Progress in Earth and Planetary Science* 7, 50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40645-020-00364-w>

- Tsirogiannis, G., Thomatou, A.-A., Psarra, E., Mazarakioti, E.C., Katerinopoulou, K., Zotos, A., Kontogeorgos, A., Patakas, A., Ladavos, A. (2022) Probabilistic Machine Learning for the Authentication of the Protected Designation of Origin of Greek Bottarga from Messolongi: A Generic Methodology to Cope with Very Small Number of Samples. *Applied Sciences* 12(13), Article 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12136335>
- Tulli, F., Moreno-Rojas, J.M., Messina, C.M., Trocino, A., Xiccato, G., Muñoz-Redondo, J.M., Santulli, A., Tibaldi, E. (2020) The Use of Stable Isotope Ratio Analysis to Trace European Sea Bass (*D. labrax*) Originating from Different Farming Systems. *Animals* 10(11), Article 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10112042>
- Twining, C.W., Taipale, S.J., Ruess, L., Bec, A., Martin-Creuzburg, D., Kainz, M.J. (2020) Stable Isotopes of Fatty Acids: Current and Future Perspectives for Advancing Trophic Ecology. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 375 (1804). doi: 10.1098/rstb.2019.0641
- Varrà, M.O., Ghidini, S., Zanardi, E., Badiana, A., Ianieri, A. (2019) Authentication of European sea bass according to production method and geographical origin by light stable isotope ratio and rare earth elements analyses combined with chemometrics. *Italian Journal of Food Safety* 8, 7872, DOI: 10.4081/ijfs.2019.7872
- Wang, Y., Cong, Y., Zhang, J., Tang, Y., Shi, X., Shi, J. (2021) Intra- and Inter-Specific Variation in Edible Jellyfish Biomarkers and Implications for Origin Traceability and Authentication. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.755048>
- Xia, Y., Jia, L., Zhang, K., Xie, J., Yu, E., Tian, J., Gong, W., Li, Z., Li, H., Wang, G., Liu, Y. (2022). Geographical Origin Traceability of *Procambarus clarkii* Based on Mineral Elements and Stable Isotopes. *Foods* 11(19), Article 19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11193060>
- Zhang, X., Cheng, J., Han, D., Zhao, X., Chen, X., Liu, Y. (2019) Geographical origin traceability and species identification of three scallops (*Patinopecten yessoensis*, *Chlamys farreri*, and *Argopecten irradians*) using stable isotope analysis. *Food Chemistry* 299, 125107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2019.125107>
- Zhang, X., Liu, Y., Li, Y., Zhao, X. (2017) Identification of the geographical origins of sea cucumber (*Apostichopus japonicus*) in northern China by using stable isotope ratios and fatty acid profiles. *Food Chemistry* 218, 269–276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.08.083>
- Zhu, Y., Newman, S.P., Reid, W.D.K., Polunin, N.V.C. (2019). Fish stable isotope community structure of a Bahamian coral reef. *Marine Biology* 166(12), 160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-019-3599-9>
- Zontov, Y.V., Rodionova, O.Y., Kucheryavskiy, S.V., Pomerantsev, A.L. (2017) DD-SIMCA – A MATLAB GUI tool for data driven SIMCA approach. *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems* 167, 23–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemolab.2017.05.010>

